

**DIDACTIC GAMES AS A MEANS OF LEARNING PRESCHOOL
CHILDREN LEARN ENGLISH***Isakulova Bakhtigul Khadjamovna**Teacher, English Department,**'Tashkent Institute of Irrigation and Agricultural Mechanization Engineers'**National Research University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan***Annotation:**

The whole system of work is aimed at realizing the main goal of education, which is the painless integration of preschoolers into the school system, a flexible transition to in-depth study of a foreign language in elementary school, and maintaining a positive motivation for studying this subject in the future.

Key words- methodology, pedagogy, didactic games, teaching a foreign language, teaching children, preschoolers, activities, actions.

Early teaching of foreign language speech to preschoolers is relevant today. This is determined by the increased status of a foreign language in modern society.

The 21st century is the heyday of information technology. The ever-expanding external economic and cultural ties of our country form a social order for the knowledge of foreign languages for their practical use in various spheres of the life of our society. As a result, there is a need for highly qualified specialists who speak foreign languages, and is determined by the increased status of a foreign (English) language as a means of intercultural communication, stimulating a powerful movement of society towards new forms and models of teaching it as a subject. Therefore, right now the concept of early learning a foreign language is considered as a component of education not only at school, but also at a preschool institution, since the study of foreign language speech at an early age is especially effective.

It is well known that preschool age is that period of human life when the basic qualities of a person are formed, the foundations of physical, emotional, and mental development are laid.

Language learning during this period gives better results, because it is carried out in a sensitive period of child development: the plasticity of the natural mechanism of language acquisition, imitation abilities, natural curiosity and the need to learn new things contribute to the

development of children's intellectual, speech and emotional abilities. (Vereshchagina I.N., Negnevitskaya E.I., Izhogina T.I., Eremina O.P., Galskova N.D., Grigoryeva E.I., Safonova V.V. Mayer A.A., Luran S., Verbovskaya M.I., Shishkova I.A., Bonk N.A., Wenger L.A., Vygotsky L.S., Galperin P.Ya., Leontiev A.A., Amonashvili Sh.A. and etc.). The possibilities of preschool age in mastering a foreign language are truly unique: "A child learns in a few months to speak a foreign language in a way that he cannot learn in a few years" (K.D. Ushinsky).

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A foreign language at an early stage is considered as a means of shaping the child's intellect and developing his abilities; as a means of awareness of one's own "I" and self-expression; as a means of social interaction through which the child masters the social world.

It opens the child to the prospect of learning a new world with its own values: nature, environment, identity. National traditions, children's folk tales, folklore. Music, poetry and songs. All this contributes to the formation of a holistic picture of the world in preschoolers to the education of tolerance towards others to the instillation of interest in learning a foreign language as a vital means of communication.

Children who learn foreign languages at preschool age develop better cognitive abilities, they master reading earlier, they are able to learn the language flexibly and at an abstract level, which is manifested in judgments about the grammar of the language, in understanding the play on words.

Early teaching of a foreign language to preschoolers provides an opportunity for a flexible transition to in-depth study of it in elementary school, and allows you to maintain a positive motivation for studying this subject in the future.

In order to effectively solve the indicated problem, various forms and methods are used in practical work with children, aimed at the formation of mental operations, speech activity, and the desire for knowledge of the surrounding reality. A special place is occupied by the game, which is a way of familiarizing with the world of adults, a way of learning.

For children of preschool age, the game is of exceptional importance: the game for them is study, the game for them is work, the game for them is a serious form of learning.

The possibility of relying on gaming activity makes it possible to provide natural motivation for speech in a foreign language, to make even the most elementary statements interesting and meaningful. The more the child immerses himself in the atmosphere of the game, following clear rules and improvising on the go, the more successful the learning is. The game in teaching English does not oppose learning activities, but is organically connected with it.

Therefore, the game methodology, namely the use of didactic games, determines the basic principle of teaching preschoolers a foreign language, since it is the didactic game that contains both the learning form and the game activity of preschoolers at the same time. Two tasks - didactic and game - reflect the relationship between learning and play.

The use of didactic games in pedagogical activity is determined by the fact that their content is based on strictly scientific knowledge and children, thus, learn the culture of scientific work.

Unlike the direct setting of a didactic task in the classroom, in a didactic game it is carried out through a game task, determines the game actions, becomes the task of the child himself, arouses the desire and need to solve it, and activates the game actions.

In didactic games, children not only develop speech activity, assimilate and consolidate lexical and grammatical material, but also develop mental processes: thinking, memory, voluntary attention, as well as important personality traits such as purposefulness, concentration, the ability to subordinate one's behavior to certain rules. and, of course, such social feelings as empathy, the ability to come to the rescue, collectivism, friendship.

The game frees children from the fear of speaking a foreign language, leaves a vivid impression of the lesson.

To effectively solve this problem, optimal pedagogical conditions, features of interaction with children and families were determined:

- The organization of the educational process has been thought through through various types of children's activities: educational, playful, creative, contributing to the unification of the mental, emotional, and motor activities of children;
- An educational, subject-developing learning environment has been created;
- A system of long-term planning has been developed; abstracts of specially organized integrated, thematic classes with the definition of game material;
- Selected didactic games that correspond to the topics of the classes, carried out their classification into groups according to the types of children's speech activity.

An essential sign of the quality of education is the interaction with parents, active participants in the pedagogical process. We organize both general and individual consultations, seminars and workshops. We invite them to classes, parent meetings, holidays.

Let us give an example of a seminar - a workshop for parents on the topic "The use of didactic games in teaching children English."

Nowadays, knowledge of English is no longer a whim or a hobby, but often a necessity. No one doubts the need to know foreign languages. This is an important condition for the development of successful socio-economic, diplomatic and intercultural relations, it is a means and method of understanding the world, as well as an important tool for the harmonious development of the individual.

Teaching children English can be carried out not only in preschool institutions, but also in family settings. To do this, it is not necessary to have a pedagogical education, it is enough to know how to organize and conduct didactic games with children at home.

Preschool childhood is a world of fairy tales, exciting games, stories and songs. World. Where the interest to play with peers reigns. That's why:

- do not rush to deprive children of this joy;
- do not be afraid that children who play too much will not learn seriousness and responsibility.

The child is perfectly able to distinguish the fictional world from the real world and transfer the skills acquired in the game to real meaningful activities.

The game method of teaching is the most effective, as it allows you to accustom to mental work gradually. It makes the lesson creative and interesting.

Of particular importance in learning is the didactic game. It contains both a learning task and a game activity, which allows you to lay the foundations of learning activities: the ability to set a goal and act in accordance with it; acquire knowledge and acquire new knowledge. Didactic game develops attention, thinking, creativity; frees children from the fear of speaking a foreign language.

Such a serious obstacle as a "language barrier" becomes easily overcome as soon as the children get into the situation of the game, they are involved in a common creative search.

Therefore, the importance of using didactic games in teaching English is especially great not only in the classroom, but also at home, while walking and relaxing.

A variety of games helps to create favorable conditions for the assimilation of new knowledge: "One and many" to consolidate the count to 10 and the formation of the plural of nouns; "Vegetable Lotto" for the activation of vocabulary on the topic "Vegetables"; "Funny animals"

during which the grammatical construction "I am a ..." is worked out; "Fold the toy" to reinforce vocabulary; "Plant a butterfly on a flower", during which the skill of using flower names in speech is consolidated; "The season", during which ideas about seasonal changes and natural phenomena are fixed, and many others.

The didactic game helps to maintain the high activity of each child, while taking into account the individual characteristics of children.

Some tips for using didactic games:

*Too excitable, mobile children often offer board-printed games: "Lotto", "Mosaic", "Cut Pictures", "Cubes" and others. Engage children with a slow reaction in games that require a quick response, solving a game problem: "Who will call faster?", "Add a word", "Answer quickly".

* With children of 6 years of age, play board games more often: to generalize the classification of objects, during which they will learn not only to speak English, but also to think. ("Collect a picture", "Pick a couple", "Merry Domino", "Magic Arrow" and many others).

*To relieve fatigue, use games with movements. Games such as Fun Carousel, Throw the Ball and Say the Word, Edible/Inedible, Mice Dance, Apples on the Floor, Charlie, What Can You Do? and others - help to increase the attention and performance of preschoolers and repeat the studied material in a fun, relaxed way.

For example, ball games (both one child and several children participate at the same time)

1. Throw the ball. Children, standing in a semicircle, throw the ball up and, while it flies, call the right word or phrase (the word is determined by which card they are shown)
2. Pass the ball to a neighbor. The teacher shows a card. The child calls a word or phrase, passing the ball to a friend standing next to him.
3. Hit the ball. Children in English name the words or phrases that they are asked to pronounce in Russian. At the same time, they must hit the ball on the ground, say the right word or phrase and catch the ball bouncing off the ground.
4. Get into the basket. Children throw the ball into a basket on the floor and at the same time name words on a certain lexical topic.
5. Roll the ball. Children sit on the floor in a circle and randomly roll the ball to each other. The person who received the ball must quickly name a word or phrase.

Board - printed games:

"Close the window"

Children are given cards - panels with the image of objects or animals, birds and chips. Next, words are pronounced on a predetermined topic, the children must close the window of the card in which the named word is shown.

"Show"

Children are given cards with the image of objects, animals, for example, poultry. The adult names the bird in English, the children raise cards with the image of the named bird.

"Touch"

An adult offers a task: the children should come to the table and touch the toy that is called to him. Then the children play in pairs: one child asks to touch the toy, the other does. Then the children change places.

The main thing to remember is that the main pedagogical value of the game is the education of the will, the ability to overcome the bitterness of defeat, the desire to play until victory. In short, these didactic games are not only interesting for children, but they are also the basis for them to acquire knowledge in the way of purposeful education, that is, to learn English. This process makes it possible for children to learn the topics easily and quickly.

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